

Adaptive Electricity Price Forecasting for EV Charging: Integrating Exogenous Forecasts and Rolling Window Training

Giorgos Roussakis
*Foundation of Research and
Technology Hellas*

Danique Thaens
*Erasmus School of Economics,
Erasmus University Rotterdam*

Tobias Kers
*Erasmus School of Economics,
Erasmus University Rotterdam*

Rommert Dekker
*Erasmus School of Economics, Erasmus
University Rotterdam*

George Tzagkarakis
Foundation of Research and Technology Hellas

ABSTRACT

Accurate electricity price forecasts are critical for optimizing flexible consumption, such as electric vehicle (EV) charging. Existing work has shown that multi-day ahead forecasts can reduce consumer costs, but two practical challenges remain. First, exogenous variables such as renewable generation, load, imports, and fuel prices are often unavailable beyond day-ahead horizons, leading researchers to rely on error-based proxies. Second, many studies train models on fixed datasets, which may limit their ability to adapt to changing market conditions. This paper proposes two extensions to address these issues. We outline an approach to incorporate multi-day forecasts of exogenous variables directly into electricity price models, and we evaluate rolling and expanding window training schemes to account for non-stationarity and seasonality. Using Dutch market data, we assess how these design choices affect both forecast accuracy and the downstream performance of forecast-based EV charging optimization. The results highlight the importance of realistic data pipelines and adaptive training strategies for improving the reliability and relevance of consumer-oriented forecasting applications.

Keywords: Electricity price forecasting, Electric vehicle (EV) charging optimization, Adaptive model training, Exogenous variables, Non-stationarity

1 Motivation and Contribution

With the emergence of bidding markets and dynamic electricity pricing, interest in electricity price forecasting has grown significantly among both energy companies and individual consumers. This trend became particularly relevant following the deregulation of European electricity markets in the 1990s and 2000s (Mulder, Shestalova and Zwart, 2006), which facilitated hourly price trading on platforms like the EPEX Spot market. In recent years, the Dutch electricity market has experienced heightened volatility (Boer, 2024), initially triggered by extreme fluctuations in gas prices following the war in Ukraine, and subsequently sustained by the ongoing transition toward weather-dependent renewable energy sources.

Dynamic pricing and growing renewable generation increase hourly price volatility, giving flexible consumers a chance to reduce costs by shifting EV charging. Prior multi-day studies often assume

perfect knowledge of exogenous variables beyond day-ahead horizons, an unrealistic convenience for operational systems. We (i) introduce a dual-stage pipeline that trains on calibrated, horizon-dependent noise applied to historical exogenous variables and (ii) evaluate rolling and expanding training approaches for multi-day horizons. We measure both forecast accuracy and practical economic value in EV charging.

2 Data and evaluation protocol

We use hourly Dutch electricity prices and exogenous variables across two independent evaluation pipelines, which inherently resolves overlapping period concerns. The first dataset augments historical exogenous variables with noise reflecting forecast uncertainty (01-2023 to 04-2025). The second uses actual week-ahead forecasts (10-2023 to 10-2025). To establish a baseline (Table 1), we applied a strict chronological, unstratified train-validation-test split (~50-25-25). For the simulated dataset, this corresponds to training on 2023 data, validating from 01-2024 to 06-2024, and testing from 07-2024 onwards, with equivalent relative splits applied to the actual forecast dataset. For our primary rolling framework, which issues 7-day forecasts, we utilized rolling-origin cross-validation to ensure robust hyperparameter selection: each hyperparameter combination was evaluated across a walk-forward sequence (6-month training window, 30-day validation window, 30-day step). This forward-rolling approach naturally exposes the models to varying seasons and volatility regimes without requiring explicit stratification. Rolling and expanding training frameworks were compared.

3 Models, probabilistic forecasts, and optimizer

Electricity price forecasting (EPF) methods are broadly classified into statistical models and machine learning techniques. Statistical models, such as ARIMA (Box and Jenkins, 1976) and GARCH (Bollerslev, 1986), have long served as benchmarks. ARIMA models often perform optimally when trained for specific hours of the day (Crespo Cuaresma *et al.*, 2004), while GARCH models are better equipped to handle the conditional heteroskedasticity and volatility spikes typical of energy markets. However, the linearity of these models is frequently cited as a drawback, as they may fail to capture the complex, non-linear patterns of hourly prices. Furthermore, the assumption of stationarity required by many statistical models is difficult to achieve in practice.

Machine learning methods have gained prominence for their ability to model non-linear relationships. Deep Neural Networks (DNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997) networks have demonstrated superior performance in various European markets due to their capacity to learn temporal dependencies in sequential data (Lago, De Ridder and De Schutter, 2018). Recent hybrid approaches, such as the combination of LSTM and XGBoost or LightGBM (Manfre Jaimes *et al.*, 2023), leverage the strengths of recurrent networks for trend capturing and gradient-boosted trees for handling extreme values and price spikes. LightGBM is particularly advantageous for consumer applications due to its leaf-wise growth strategy, which offers approximately 20 times faster training than traditional level-wise algorithms while maintaining similar accuracy levels. Despite these advancements, a gap exists in multi-day forecasting where exogenous variables like wind and solar generation are often treated as perfectly known, a luxury not available in real-world scenarios beyond the 24-hour horizon.

To address the uncertainty inherent in multi-day horizons, this study incorporates probabilistic methods to move beyond simple point estimates. Distributional Deep Neural Networks (DDNN) (Marcjasz *et al.*, 2023) are utilized to parameterize full probability distributions, effectively capturing the heteroskedasticity and heavy tails of electricity prices. These are complemented by Lasso Quantile Regression Averaging (LQRA) (Uniejewski and Weron, 2021), which aggregates individual model outputs into a single probabilistic forecast while utilizing Lasso regularization for optimal model selection. By quantifying predictive uncertainty, these models facilitate the stochastic optimization of EV charging, allowing the system to hedge against price volatility and spikes that deterministic point-forecast models fail to account for.

The core objective of the optimization is to minimize the total electricity expenditure over the forecast horizon while ensuring the vehicle's energy requirements are met for all scheduled trips. We distinguish between two mathematical approaches based on the type of forecast used. For point forecasts, a deterministic linear programming formulation is employed, where the model assumes the predicted price is the realized price. For probabilistic forecasts, we implement a stochastic programming approach using Sample Average Approximation (SAA). This allows the optimizer to consider the entire distribution of possible price outcomes, effectively hedging against the risk of extreme price spikes by favoring charging periods that are consistently low across various scenarios.

The optimization is governed by several critical physical and operational constraints that ensure the practical relevance of the results. First, the state-of-charge (SoC) of the vehicle's 75 kWh battery is strictly managed. To prevent accelerated battery degradation, the SoC is constrained between a lower bound of 20% and an upper bound of 80%, except when a long-distance trip requires a higher initial charge. Second, the model must satisfy the energy demand of a fixed trip schedule, where energy consumption is calculated based on a specific efficiency of 0.1875 kWh/km. Charging is restricted by the power capacity of a standard 11 kW home charger and is only permitted during hours when the vehicle is physically connected to the grid.

4 Key Results

Forecast skill. Incorporating actual week-ahead exogenous forecasts into the evaluation pipeline substantially reduces week-ahead RMSE across models compared to methods that rely on error-based proxies. Tree-based models lead performance with probabilistic methods near the top. Training models from scratch using a rolling window yields only modest multi-day accuracy improvements over static training. This is largely because the provision of high-quality exogenous forecasts already establishes a highly accurate baseline, and high-capacity models adequately capture fundamental market dynamics during their initial training. Nonetheless, this rolling approach remains practically valuable for adapting to structural breaks or sudden spikes in market volatility. Expanding windows show diminishing returns given higher computational cost and thus were omitted from the final table.

Model	Data with Simulated Forecasts	Data with Observed Forecasts	Data with Observed Forecasts, trained with rolling windows
ARIMA	44.45	39.83	40.75
GARCH	47.91	41.53	41.67
XGB	36.24	26.03	26.14
LGBM	35.88	26.20	26.33
LSTM	47.76	32.10	27.95
DNN	49.90	49.63	47.75
DDNN	46.53	28.00	27.12
LQRA	35.90	29.57	29.14

Table 1: Week-Ahead RMSE for evaluated models. Units: €/Mwh.

Economic value. Forecast-based charging reduces weekly EV charging costs dramatically compared to naive strategies. Deterministic day-ahead optimization halves costs relative to simple heuristics; probabilistic optimization with realistic exogenous forecasts approaches the ideal full-information benchmark. Rolling window training produces small additional cost savings over static models.

	Default Charging	Simple Minimum Cost	Day-Ahead Optimization	Full Information	LQRA(median)
Week Ahead prediction	359.21	221.10	115.35	61.47	69.15

Table 2: Total charging costs (€) excluding tax for benchmark and best forecast-based strategy.

5 Practical implications and computational considerations

Training with realistic exogenous uncertainty is more valuable than marginal gains from more complex architectures for multi-day horizons. The rolling training approach offers a practical tradeoff: it adapts to recent market shifts with limited computational overhead, unlike expanding windows which increase training time substantially for little accuracy gain. For consumer applications, these findings recommend lightweight periodic model updates (trained from scratch) with realistic exogenous input pipelines. Data were collected from the ENTSOE Transparency platform and API. Forecasts have become increasingly more granular, up to 10-minute data, but the range of actual forecasts like the ones used in this study are limited to 2023 using the API.

6 Conclusions

This study demonstrates that bridging the gap between theoretical models and practical constraints significantly enhances the utility of electricity price forecasting for flexible consumers. By accounting for market non-stationarity via rolling window schemes and moving beyond the standard day-ahead horizon, we enable a strategic "proactive" charging approach that allows electric vehicle (EV) owners to bypass high-price periods entirely. While gains are modest in the Dutch case, adaptive rolling training remains important for structural breaks. Additionally, evaluating probabilistic forecasts in real-world consumer settings provides vital insights into their practical utility.

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REFERENCES

- Boer, S. de (2024) "The Dutch Electricity Sector – Part 4: Changing Electricity Markets Present Opportunities and Risks for Businesses and Households," *RaboResearch* [Preprint].
- Bollerslev, T. (1986) "Generalized autoregressive conditional heteroskedasticity," *Journal of econometrics*, 31(3), pp. 307–327.
- Box, G. and Jenkins, G. (1976) "Analysis: Forecasting and Control," *San Francisco* .
- Chen, T. and Guestrin, C. (2016) "XGBoost: A scalable tree boosting system," *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, pp. 785–794.
- Crespo Cuaresma, J. et al. (2004) "Forecasting electricity spot-prices using linear univariate time-series models," *Applied Energy*, 77(1), pp. 87–106.
- Hochreiter, S. and Schmidhuber, J. (1997) "Long short-term memory," *Neural Computation*, 9(8), pp. 1735–1780.
- Ke, G. et al. (2017) "LightGBM: A Highly Efficient Gradient Boosting Decision Tree," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*.
- Lago, J., De Ridder, F. and De Schutter, B. (2018) "Forecasting spot electricity prices: Deep learning approaches and empirical comparison of traditional algorithms," *Applied Energy*, 221, pp. 386–405.
- Manfre Jaimes, D. et al. (2023) "A hybrid model for multi-day-ahead electricity price forecasting considering price spikes," *Forecasting*, 5(3), pp. 499–521.
- Marcjasz, G. et al. (2023) "Distributional neural networks for electricity price forecasting," *Energy Economics*, 125, p. 106843.
- Mulder, M., Shestalova, V. and Zwart, G. (2006) "Liberalisation of European energy markets: challenges and policy options."
- Uniejewski, B. and Weron, R. (2021) "Regularized quantile regression averaging for probabilistic electricity price forecasting," *Energy Economics*, 95, p. 105121.